

UZBEKISTAN-KOREA: CURRENT AND PROSPECTS OF MUTUAL COOPERATION

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ФРАЗ В КОРЕЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

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Аннотация. Тема важных фраз в лингвистике подробно изучается в разделе, посвященном фразеологии. Как и во всех языках, эти выражения широко используются в узбекском и корейском языках. Есть фразы, доступные на обоих языках, а также множество фразеологизмов с отличительными особенностями. Эта статья посвящена фразам, изученным узбекскими и корейскими лингвистами, их истории происхождения и использованию.

Ключевые слова: лингвистика, фразеология, идиомы, корейские идиомы, китайские идиомы.

THE STUDY OF PHRASES IN KOREAN LINGUISTICS

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Annotation. The topic of important phrases in linguistics is studied in detail in the section on phraseology. As in all languages, the expressions are widely used in Korean. There are phrases available in both languages, as well as a variety of phraseologies with distinctive features. This article focuses on the phrases studied by Uzbek and Korean linguists, their history of origin, and their use.

Keywords: linguistics, phraseology, idioms, idioms, Korean, Chinese idioms.

Phrases play an important role in Korean linguistics. Korean speakers often use idioms in their daily lives. These expressions are understood and used easily by other native Korean speakers, but they are very difficult for foreigners. Idioms are commonly used expressions that consist of two or more specific

words or phrases that mean something. It has absolutely nothing to do with the definition of each of these words or phrases, phrases are regularly used in every country and have been developed over a long period to express certain meanings, so in this article, we will discuss the difference between Korean and we try to compare the similarities.

Phrases related to body parts are Chinese idioms for Korean and Chinese students to better understand and learn idioms easily. The largest number of expressions refer to body parts. Also, several scientific works and research related to expressions have been carried out. Most previous studies on idioms have compared Chinese and Korean idioms. The role of linguists such as Gyeji Ung, Rojeong Wang, Nam Lee, and Jeongjeong Jin is incomparable in this. This reflects the close historical and cultural ties between Korea and China, as well as the increasing number of students learning each other's languages through exchanges between the two countries.

It should be noted that the linguist scientist Kim Moon Jang began to study expressions related to the human body part “hand” in 1960, after that in 1990 then many scholars began to study expressions related to the body. Among them, Lee Kyung Ja studied expressions related to body parts during his scientific career. In the center of his research process, he puts expressions related to “head”, “eye”, “ear”, “nose”, “mouth” and “hand” in the main place. The goal was to activate the use of such expressions in everyday life. Research on idiomatic expressions in Korean as a foreign language other than Korean is relatively scarce, covering everything from basic idiomatic terms to teaching methods for idiomatic expressions. The Concept of Idiomatic Expressions The conceptual location of idiomatic expressions varies from the discussion of Korean linguistics to the quality of Korean as a foreign language. Although there has been a lot of research on Korean idioms, the use of terms is inconsistent and confusing.

The difference in terminology through previous studies is as follows: in 2001 Moon Geum-Hyeon reviewed the idiomatic expression of education in Korean language education and pointed out the terms and concepts used in different classrooms as a problem. Elementary school textbook – “Idiom” is a word that is widely used in everyday life. High School – Using the term “Idiom”, it is made up of two or more words and the meaning of the whole can be known only from the meaning of each word. Defined as “an expression expressing a special meaning that does not exist”, the term “idiom” is used for purely idiomatic expressions. Middle School - Although the term “idiomatic phrase” is used in the Korean language field, this concept is different from the idiomatic

expressions discussed, as it mainly relates to poetic phrases that are often used idiomatically. On the other hand, by using the term “Idiom Expression” as meaning similar to an idiom, two or more words such as idiom and idiom are combined to form a single meaning. There seems to be a lack of consistency in wording. The terminology used to express idiomatic expressions is mainly based on terminologists Gwan Yong-gu No Su-Ryun (1936), Lee Hun-jong (1961), Kim Min-Su (1964), Nae-yong (1989)), Lee Hee-ja (1994), Park Se-Yong (2001)) Idiomatic (broad) Kim Min-soo (1964), Kim Jong-taek (1971), Kim Moon-chang (1974), Lee Hae-won (1987) 1985), Hong Mi -rang (1989), Heo Young (1989), Choi Kyung-bong (1992), Park Hye-Kyung (1994), Hwang Soo-mi (1994), Moon Jong-son (1994), Kim Mi-ryun (1994)), Park Se-young (2001), Kim Jun-ki and Kim Hyang-suk (2003) Idioms Minsu Kim (1964), Moonchang Kim (1974), Jaegi Shim (1986), Annyeonghwa (1987) Expressions of idioms Hyeonhwa Kang (1988), studied by Lee Sang-eok (1993).

The first relevant method in the study of idioms can be seen in the example of Lee Young-Suk (1992), but did not discuss specific teaching methods. However, in 2003, linguist Hyeon-Yong used video materials to explain to students. In 1998, Yoo Dok Jae also analyzed the phrases and revealed the problems of textbooks related to the existing phrase. Moon Geum-heon presented a list of idioms found in existing Korean language textbooks in 1998, showing the specific features and problems of the textbook and finally suggested ways to study idioms. In 2003, Cho Hyeon Yong introduced terms similar to body idioms to the public by analyzing idiomatic expressions related to non-verbal behavior. In 2001, Jeon Hye Yong mentioned the five stages of expressions and proposed to teach them on this basis. In 2003, Hu Mun Ok put forward the idea that it is necessary to teach phrases related to the Chinese language and tried to create several programs for this. As can be seen from the above, research on idiom education is primarily limited to discussion of body idioms. Second, it was discussed by targeting common phrases. In this way, we will take a broader look at the research of the above scientists. In the case of Deokja Yu (1998), only a teaching method was presented without a step-by-step list of idioms, while Geum-Hyeon Moon (1998) pointed out the problem after analyzing the current situation. But textbooks and step-by-step lists of phrases and crime prevention training systems are of particular importance. However, since the category of tolerance is not defined, this has been pointed out as a problem, as the list of idioms includes not only similes but also proverbs, which Moon Geum-Hyeon (1996) already suggested should be excluded from the category of idioms. To Cho Hyun- Yong (2000), general vocabulary is the

subject of education, so the expression tutoring system is unique. Not only is this not true, but Moon Geum-Hyeon (1998) doesn't diverge significantly from the below. Jeon Hye-youthful (2001) presented the meaning of the literacy stage of private expression. The donation is divided into phases, the confirmation practice phase, and the integrated operation phase. In particular, in the stage of integrated operation, expressions are classified and presented according to pronunciation functions similar as appointment, fraud, and advice. It encourages the practical use of expressions in speech situations. Eventually, Confucianism (2003) presented a crime forestallment expression with a focus on being a Chinese learner.

In Korean, phraseological units and phraseological combinations are considered to be one type of 관용어, which causes numerous controversial issues, in particular, whether to consider 관용어 as phraseological combinations or private expressions. We should note that the private restatement of the Greek expression is a point of originality. Consider phraseological units using the illustration of (관용어) in Korean, although the list of phraseological units is complicated because in Korean there are phraseological units formed from Chinese characters. An expression is a combination of verbal units, the meaning of which doesn't coincide with the meaning of its constituent rudiments is an integer in meaning turns, we cannot decide the meaning of which from the meanings of the words included in them.

눈코 뜰 새 없다 – “no time to lift your eyes and nose” = to be veritably busy.

손을 쓰다 – “to use the handy” to impact circumstances.

허리띠를 졸라매다 – “belt - tensing” = to save, deprive oneself of any pleasures. In the below private combinations, decomposability is especially enhanced by adding patches of the accusative case 을/를, therefore establishing the integrity of the expression. As you know, intralingual and interlingua expressions differ. Interlinguistic verbal expressions are characterized by non-free word combinations and the convergence of meaning, while interlingua expressions are characterized by the impossibility of nonfictional restatement. The combination of words together forms expressions. Some expressions are free, others serve in connection. In expressions of a free connection, an independent meaning is saved and each unit performs the function of a separate member of the judgment, similar as

책을 읽는다 - Reading a book;

신문을 본다 - I look at the review;

그림을 그린다 – I draw.

Combinations called on-free, connected words are more frequently considered phraseological combinations. In similar combinations, words, when combined, lose their verbal meaning and form a new semantic total, which, according to semantics, is equated to a separate word, for illustration:

눈이 높다 – “having high norms”;

발이 넓다 - “numerous familiarity.”

Phraseologies, a phraseological unit, is a common name for semantically on-free combinations of words that aren't produced in speech (as syntactic structures analogous in form- expressions or rulings), but are reproduced in it in a socially assigned stable rate of semantic content and a certain verbal grammatical structure. Phraseologies and expressions, among other effects, can be divided into groups in terms of origin and tradition of use. When studying languages with different structures, first of all, the nature of the correspondence of the element composition of languages is taken into account, in which variants are generally distinguished verbal, grammatical, and wordbooks-grammatical. The verbal variant is a difference in the element composition of a phraseological unit, for illustration 눈이 높다(lit. “eyes high”) - in the meaning of “turn up your nose.” or 등골에 소름이 끼치다 (lit. “goosebumps appear on the reverse”) - in the meaning of “goosebumps run down the reverse.” alphabet variants are differences by verb forms and case consummations of nouns, similar as 간이 크다 (lit. “big liver”) – in the meaning of “not a skittish ten.” In some phraseological units, analogous features are relatively easily revealed, for illustration:

일을 하기 위해 적극적으로 행동하다 “Having removed the legs to appear” in the meaning of “take an active part in the performance of any work”;

발이 넓다 - 알고 지내는 사람이 많다. in the meaning of “broad leg” - to have numerous familiarity – “to be sociable”;

배가아프다 - 남이 잘되어서 질투가 in the meaning of “stomach hurts” - to begrudge someone's success;

너무 우스워서 배를 움켜잡고 웃다 “snare the nexus”- when it's ridiculous, laugh, clinging the stomach – “burst with horselaugh.”

Lexica-grammatical variants of the difference suggest a difference in the structure of phraseological units, for illustration, 눈 깜짝할 사이(lit. “eye blink gap”) “in the blink of an eye.” Considering phraseological units as an artistic subcaste of the language, we can conclude that connotation plays an important part in the conformation of artistic and public semantics, reflecting a certain

vision of the world through the prism of the public language. According to exploration workshop, phraseological units are most frequently set up in fabrication, journalism, in colloquial speech, we associate the use of phraseological units with their suggestive capabilities. Figurativeness, expression, as we noted over, which is characteristic of a significant part of phraseological turns, helps to avoid stereotyping, and lack of emotion in speech communication. Phraseological units of an erudite nature, have an “increased” suggestive and stylistic coloring, their use gives speech solemnity, poetry, and enlightenment. For phraseological units of a colloquial-everyday plan, a “reduced” suggestive-style coloring is characteristic, which makes it possible to express irony, familiarity, disdain, etc. The study of set expressions showed that linguacultural features of the language should be taken into account. Taking into account the features of the Korean language will allow a deeper study of phraseology and other affiliated languages, to consider the semantic and happy eventuality of phraseological units in an oral speech to convey not only the suggestive-emotional state but also the absoluteness of the content of the statement.

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